

Carrot cultivation technology

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Abstract: Homegrown carrots are crisper, fresher, and come in a much wider variety of flavors, colors, and shapes than what you can buy in the average supermarket. We link to vendors to help you find relevant products. If you buy from one of our links, we may earn a commission. .

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Cultivation and History. Close your eyes for just a moment and think of a carrot. What do you see? I’m going to take a wild guess and assume that you thought of something orange in color. So it may surprise you to know that the wild ancestor of our domestic carrot, *D. carota*, has a white root. The orange color we associate with this vegetable is a fairly recent development in the history of the domestic carrot. Researchers seem to be unsure just how far back domestication of this root vegetable took place. In an issue of *Chronica HORTICULTURAE* from 2011, John Stolarczyk

and Jules Janick point to evidence that domestic carrots have been around since at least the second century CE. There is a consensus among experts, however, that a thousand years ago people were eating yellow and purple carrots in Central Asia, the place where they are thought to have been originally cultivated – or perhaps as far back as 5000 years ago.

It wasn't until much later that orange varieties came onto the scene. In "Origin and Distribution of the Western Cultivated Carrot," author Otto Banga cites the first historical evidence – from written accounts and paintings – of the orange carrot in the 1600's. According to Banga, orange pigmentation in carrots came about through mutation and selection of a strain of yellow carrots. Knowing just a bit about the history of carrots should give us a greater appreciation for both the bright orange ones we are all familiar with, and varieties in other beautiful colors.

How to Sow

Whether you want to grow carrots that are orange, black, or something else on the color spectrum, you'll need to know how to start them from seed. Carrots do not transplant well – the roots are sensitive to disturbance, so seed sowing is a must.

Choose your seeds and select a garden spot with full sun, one where you can create a carrot paradise. This paradise will consist of loose, sandy loam soil that is well-draining. It should be free from rocks, roots, and clods of dirt to about 12 inches deep. Pull up any weeds if you see them as well. Plan to sow your carrot seeds as soon as your soil can be worked. For a spring garden this is usually 2-4 weeks before your last frost date. You can also sow them 10-12 weeks before your first frost date for a fall harvest.

If you are planting in rows, space them 10 inches apart. Pat the soil gently without compressing it, then lay out your seeds. Plant 2-6 seeds per inch. Cover with 1/4-1/2 inch of soil, then pat the soil again gently. Carrots also grow well in containers, and potted carrots can even be grown indoors – in fact, they are one of the easiest veggies to grow inside, and their leafy green foliage makes them an attractive plant for the home. Just make sure your carrots are on a sunny windowsill and keep them watered. Water lightly, since carrot seeds are small and light, and prone to being washed away. Keep the soil moist, but not waterlogged – you may need to water every day until germination.

Carrot seeds can take up to 21 days or longer to germinate, so this is a good time to exercise your patience and complete some other gardening tasks.

Soil

Work well-matured compost or vermicompost into your soil to prepare it for planting. Make sure there are no large clods in your compost, as this will cause misshapen roots. If you add manure, make sure it is aged – high nitrogen levels are detrimental to root development.

This root vegetable requires phosphorus for healthy growth. If a soil test reveals that your soil is lacking in phosphorus, work some bone meal into your soil when you prepare it for planting.

Growing Tips Interplant with radish seeds as nurse plants. Radishes grow faster than carrots, and their roots loosen the soil and prevent weeds. Cover your newly seeded area with burlap to keep the soil moist. Check daily, and remove when seeds germinate. Grow in raised beds or containers if your soil is too heavy. Succession plant every 4-6 weeks for a continuous harvest. Homegrown carrots are known to split and crack; we have a guide to help you to prevent this from happening.

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